

Reproducibility Certificate

This is to certify that the results in the paper below have been assessed and found to meet the requirements of the cascada reproducibility policy for a rating of RRR.

Non-Standard Errors

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Major Concerns:

None. We reproduced the results with perfect accuracy.

Minor Concerns: